

IMPLEMENTING A WORKPLACE FITNESS AND WELLNESS PROGRAM FOR LIBRARIANS

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ABSTRACT

Employee wellness is essential in maintaining workplace productivity and job satisfaction. Librarians, due to the sedentary nature of their work, face physical health challenges that can affect their well-being and performance. This study assessed the physical wellness of librarians at the University of the Assumption and proposed a Workplace Fitness and Wellness Program to address identified gaps. Using a descriptive quantitative research design, the study found that while librarians exhibit moderate physical wellness, improvements in regular exercise, sleep quality, weight management, and ergonomic practices are necessary. The proposed program includes fitness challenges, on-site exercise sessions, ergonomic assessments, and nutrition awareness initiatives to promote a healthier work environment. The findings highlight the need for structured workplace interventions tailored for librarians to enhance overall wellness and productivity. The study recommends continuous monitoring and evaluation of wellness initiatives to ensure long-term effectiveness.

Keywords: *Workplace wellness, physical fitness, librarians, employee well-being, ergonomic assessment*

INTRODUCTION

Employee wellness is a crucial factor in maintaining workplace productivity, job satisfaction, and overall well-being. In recent years, organizations across various

industries have increasingly recognized the importance of implementing structured fitness and wellness programs to support their employees' health. Despite this growing emphasis on workplace wellness, many professionals in desk-bound occupations, including librarians, often face significant physical health challenges due to prolonged sitting, repetitive tasks, and limited opportunities for movement. These conditions can lead to issues such as fatigue, musculoskeletal strain, and decreased overall well-being, ultimately affecting work performance.

Librarians play a vital role in providing information services, facilitating research, and supporting academic and institutional growth. However, the nature of their work requires long hours of sedentary activity, minimal physical movement, and extended screen time, increasing the risk of physical health issues. While wellness programs are widely implemented in corporate and healthcare settings, there is a noticeable gap in structured fitness and wellness initiatives tailored specifically for library professionals. Addressing this gap is essential to promoting a healthier work environment and improving the overall well-being of librarians.

This study seeks to develop and implement a Workplace Fitness and Wellness Program specifically designed for librarians. The program aims to encourage physical activity, reduce health risks, and enhance workplace engagement by integrating activities such as fitness challenges, on-site exercise sessions, ergonomic assessments, and health-conscious workplace initiatives. Conducting this study is necessary to identify the specific wellness needs of librarians and provide evidence-based recommendations for improving their health and productivity.

The findings of this study will be beneficial for library administrators, policymakers, and human resource professionals in designing and implementing workplace wellness initiatives. Addressing the unique challenges faced by librarians, the program has the potential to foster a more supportive and health-conscious work environment, ensuring that employees maintain both their physical and professional well-being.

Literature Review

Workplace fitness programs have evolved significantly over the decades. Their origins can be traced back to executive fitness programs introduced after World War II, when business leaders sought to promote healthy lifestyles in the workplace. Over time, these programs expanded beyond executives to include all employees, evolving into the corporate wellness initiatives seen today.

Employee wellness programs are initiatives undertaken by employers to enhance the overall health and well-being of their workforce. These programs aim to address specific health-related concerns while promoting a healthier lifestyle among employees (Corporate Finance Institute, 2025).

In recent years, organizations have increasingly recognized the importance of fostering a culture of wellness by developing comprehensive programs that focus on

multiple dimensions of health, including physical, social, mental, occupational, and financial well-being (Davidson, 2019). These initiatives not only contribute to individual health improvements but also enhance workplace productivity and job satisfaction.

A historical analysis of workplace wellness activities since the 1950s suggests that corporate wellness programs have often benefited companies more than employees (Merriwether, 2021). Despite this, the importance of workplace health and wellness programs remains widely recognized, particularly as they contribute to employee well-being, productivity, and overall job satisfaction. Corporate fitness programs have become a common feature in workplace settings, with approximately 70% of medium to large corporations offering health and fitness initiatives (Bjerke et al., 2021). More recently, these programs have expanded beyond corporate environments to include hospitals and higher education institutions, reflecting a growing recognition of the role of occupational health and wellness across different industries.

As wellness programs expand, employers face the challenge of selecting activities that genuinely engage employees. While an increasing number of fitness and wellness options cater to diverse interests, it remains critical to determine which initiatives effectively drive participation and which fail to generate enthusiasm (Von Bank & Zygmunt, 2020). Ensuring that wellness programs are both appealing and beneficial requires careful planning and consideration of employee needs and preferences.

The structure and effectiveness of workplace wellness programs vary considerably. Research highlights the importance of reporting and documentation in evaluating program success, as these processes help organizations understand the mechanisms that drive employee participation and wellness outcomes (Oliver et al., 2019). Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic reinforced the significance of occupational health and safety, prompting organizations to prioritize employee well-being and implement more structured workplace wellness initiatives (Bello et al., 2022).

Investment in workplace health and wellness programs conveys a strong commitment to employee well-being. A well-designed work environment, including well-lit spaces, fitness rooms, and employee lounges, contributes to higher staff morale and job satisfaction. Research indicates that the physical workspace—such as lighting, temperature, air quality, and noise levels—directly affects productivity and mental health (Lehman, 2014; Dumitriu, 2025). Optimizing these factors has been shown to enhance employees' well-being and organizational efficiency. Additionally, studies reveal that a significant portion of employees attribute their job satisfaction to office design, with 91% of mid- to senior-level managers acknowledging its direct impact on staff performance (Lehman, 2014). Similarly, Quintero and Castro (2022) assert that the implementation of workplace wellness programs leads to better employee health outcomes, reduced absenteeism, and improved organizational productivity.

Overall, workplace fitness and wellness programs play a crucial role in fostering a healthier and more engaged workforce. While historically centered on corporate profitability, these programs have gradually shifted toward a holistic approach that

balances employee well-being with organizational success. Ensuring that wellness initiatives are comprehensive, well-documented, and responsive to employees' needs is key to their long-term effectiveness.

Research Questions

The study aims to assess the financial wellness of librarians at the University of the Assumption with the view of drafting a financial wellness program:

Specifically, it aims to answer the following:

1. How may the physical wellness of library staff be assessed and described?
2. What activities may be proposed for library staff to improve their physical wellness?
3. What workplace fitness and wellness program can possibly be formulated for the improvement of library staff's wellness?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research design, specifically the descriptive method. Quantitative research is a systematic approach to gathering and analyzing data that focuses on numerical measurements and statistical analysis. It aims to quantify observations and gather measurable data to formulate facts and uncover patterns in research (Creswell, 2014). The descriptive method, a type of quantitative research, aims to accurately portray the characteristics of a particular individual, situation, or group. It focuses on describing and summarizing existing conditions, behaviors, or phenomena (Trochim, 2006).

Respondents

The respondents of this study comprised all library staff of the University of the Assumption from the grade school, junior high school, and the Cinense Library.

Research Instrument

The 2018 Personal Wellness Assessment, which encompasses eight dimensions of wellness, served as the primary data-gathering tool, with a specific focus on the physical wellness dimension.

Data Collection

Questionnaires were administered to all librarians at the University of the Assumption.

Data Analysis

Data were tabulated, calculated, and statistically analyzed. Frequency counts, percentage distributions, means, and standard deviations were used to discuss and interpret the findings.

RESULTS

As it can be gleaned from Table 1, the respondents demonstrate a moderate level of physical wellness with a score of 30 out of 40. While exhibiting positive habits such as seeking professional medical advice and prioritizing hydration, the respondents could benefit from increasing their level of regular exercise, improving sleep quality, exploring healthier weight management strategies, and consistently practicing sun protection. Additionally, further enhancing their overall eating patterns by incorporating a variety of nutritious foods is recommended.

Table 1
Physical Dimension of Wellness

PHYSICAL	Scores
I manage my weight in healthy ways.	3
I exercise regularly.	2
I get 7-9 hours of sleep each night and feel rested in the morning.	2
I seek advice from health care professionals if I have a health concern I cannot solve on my own.	3
I do not use or avoid harmful use of drugs (over-the-counter, prescription and illicit).	3
I drink alcohol responsibly (i.e. designated sober driver, avoid binge drinking, etc.)	3
I protect my skin from sun damage by using sunscreen with SPF 30+, wearing hats and/or avoiding tanning booths and sun lamps.	3
I maintain healthy eating patterns that include fruits and vegetables.	3
I stay hydrated and drink water throughout the day.	4
I protect myself from STIs and unwanted pregnancy by either abstaining from sexual behavior or using proper protection, such as condoms.	4
TOTAL	30

The proposed activities for the Workplace Fitness and Wellness Program as presented on Table 2 focus on enhancing the physical wellness of librarians by integrating health-conscious initiatives into their daily work environment.

Key activities include Fitness Challenges, which encourage staff to participate in group exercises or friendly competitions to promote regular physical activity. These

challenges not only improve physical health but also foster teamwork and camaraderie among colleagues.

Additionally, On-site Fitness Classes During Breaks provide convenient opportunities for librarians to engage in guided physical activities such as stretching, yoga, or light aerobics. These sessions help alleviate stress, improve posture, and boost energy levels throughout the workday.

To further support a healthier workplace, Healthy Snack Options in the Staff Break Room will be made available. Providing nutritious food choices encourages employees to adopt better eating habits, contributing to sustained energy levels and overall well-being.

Table 2
Proposed Activities for Workplace Fitness and Wellness Program

Dimension of Wellness	Proposed Activities
Physical	Fitness challenges, on-site fitness classes during breaks, healthy snack options in the staff break room.

Table 3 presents the proposed Workplace Fitness and Wellness Program aims to enhance the physical wellness of librarians by promoting an active and healthy lifestyle through structured initiatives.

The program includes Fitness Challenges, which encourage participation in group activities or competitions to motivate employees to engage in regular physical exercise and adopt healthier habits. Additionally, On-site Fitness Classes, such as yoga and Zumba, provide accessible and convenient opportunities for librarians to incorporate movement into their daily routines.

To ensure a comfortable and ergonomically sound work environment, Ergonomic Assessments will be conducted. These assessments will evaluate workstation setups and provide recommendations for improving posture, reducing strain, and enhancing overall workplace comfort.

Table 3
A Proposed Workplace Fitness and Wellness Program

Physical Wellness	To enhance the physical wellness of librarians	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fitness Challenges: Organize group activities or competitions to promote physical activity and healthy habits. • On-site Fitness Classes: Offer yoga, Zumba, or other exercise classes at the library. • Ergonomic Assessments: Evaluate workstations and provide recommendations for optimal comfort and posture.
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DISCUSSION

The assessment results indicate that respondents demonstrate a moderate level of physical wellness, scoring 30 out of 40. Strengths include seeking professional medical advice and maintaining proper hydration, suggesting that librarians are conscious of their health and wellness. However, there are notable areas for improvement, particularly in increasing regular physical activity, improving sleep quality, managing weight effectively, practicing sun protection, and maintaining a well-balanced diet. These gaps highlight the need for targeted workplace interventions to foster healthier habits among librarians.

To address these concerns, a structured Workplace Fitness and Wellness Program has been proposed. This program incorporates fitness challenges, on-site fitness classes, and access to healthy snacks, providing librarians with opportunities to enhance their physical health while balancing their professional responsibilities.

One of the key initiatives is the implementation of Fitness Challenges, which promote a culture of active living through group activities and friendly competitions. These challenges enhance cardiovascular health, boost energy levels, and foster a sense of camaraderie among colleagues. Complementing these efforts, On-site Fitness Classes, including yoga, stretching, and Zumba, provide librarians with convenient and accessible ways to engage in structured physical activity. These activities not only improve physical endurance but also reduce workplace stress and enhance overall well-being.

Furthermore, the program emphasizes workplace ergonomics to address the sedentary nature of library work. The introduction of Ergonomic Assessments aims to improve workstation setups, reduce musculoskeletal strain, and ensure that employees maintain proper posture. Implementing these assessments will enhance workplace comfort and contribute to long-term physical health.

Another significant component is the availability of healthy snack options in staff break rooms, encouraging librarians to make nutritious food choices that support sustained energy levels and cognitive function throughout the workday. By integrating these wellness strategies into the workplace, the program promotes sustainable lifestyle changes, improving both physical health and job performance.

Conclusions

The findings reveal that while librarians demonstrate moderate physical wellness, there is room for improvement in several key areas, including regular exercise, sleep quality, weight management, sun protection, and dietary habits. These findings underscore the need for structured workplace interventions to support employees in adopting healthier lifestyles.

The proposed Workplace Fitness and Wellness Program offers a comprehensive approach to addressing these wellness gaps through fitness challenges, on-site exercise classes, ergonomic assessments, and access to healthy snacks. By integrating these

initiatives into the workplace, librarians are provided with the necessary resources to enhance their physical well-being, ultimately leading to reduced health risks, improved productivity, and greater job satisfaction.

Recommendations

To ensure the successful implementation of the Workplace Fitness and Wellness Program, the following recommendations are proposed:

Regular Fitness Challenges. Organize periodic physical activity competitions or step challenges to encourage sustained participation in physical exercise.

On-site Fitness Sessions. Offer weekly yoga, stretching, or aerobic sessions to accommodate different fitness levels and schedules.

Ergonomic Evaluations. Conduct workstation assessments to minimize physical strain and promote proper posture, reducing the risk of work-related musculoskeletal disorders.

Nutrition Awareness Initiatives. Provide healthy snack options in break rooms and conduct workshops on healthy eating habits to encourage better dietary choices.

Wellness Monitoring and Feedback. Regularly assess program effectiveness through employee feedback surveys and physical health assessments to refine and improve wellness initiatives over time.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study prioritized the ethical treatment of participants, ensuring that their rights and well-being were safeguarded throughout the research process. Participation was entirely voluntary and free of charge, with potential respondents receiving a clear explanation of the program's benefits before agreeing to participate. Only librarians who provided informed consent were included in the study.

To maintain privacy and confidentiality, all personal and financial information shared by participants was handled with strict discretion. Identifiable data were anonymized, and access was restricted to authorized personnel only.

To address potential conflicts of interest and ensure objective assessments, a professional counselor conducted the personal financial evaluations. Additionally, an independent evaluator was engaged to assess the program's effectiveness and provide unbiased feedback. These measures ensured the integrity and fairness of the study while upholding ethical research standards.

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